

ON LIMITATIONS OF TWO TYPES OF BACKLUND TRANSFORMATIONS FOR FINDING EXACT SOLUTIONS OF NONLINEAR PARTIAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Abstract

In Backlund transformation method that developed by A.V.Backlund a second order partial differential equation is transformed to a pair of first order coupled nonlinear partial differential equations. This method further modified by Clariin for connecting exact solutions of two different partial differential equations . The limitations of these two methods of transformations is discussed in this study by comparing with Lie's Similarity Transformation method of solving partial differential equations . It is shown that Backlund transformations never able to find complete solutions of nonlinear partial differential equations due to loss of symmetries in the process of converting to a pair of coupled first order partial differential equations. Also shown that solutions generating by Backlund transformations and Lie's Similarity Transformations form two mutually exclusive sets in the complete solutions set of a nonlinear partial differential equation

Keywords: Backlund, Klein-Gordon, Transformation, Similarity transformation, Infinitesimals, Clariin, Weiss, Painleve Analysis, Symmetries

I. Introduction

A general method of solving an arbitrary nonlinear partial differential equations (NPDEs), especially of dispersive types is still not well developed. At present, there are few methods known for finding exact particular solutions especially solitary travelling wave type solutions, like Inverse Scattering Transform (IST) [], Backlund Transformation (BT)[]. Hirota Bilinear transformation [] Lie's Similarity Transformation (LST) [], etc. But no theory is developed to unify all these method or conditions or restrictions of adopting any particular method for a given NPDE. During last five decades the study of NPDEs mainly focused on some special class of solitary travelling wave solutions of dispersive type equations having characterized by their localized wave pulse that never change their shapes for long time scale and even after collision with same type waves. Such solitary travelling wave solutions are called solitons having many applications in different area like water waves, crystal optics, Lattice dynamics, active optical transmission lines, quantum mechanics of particles, nerve pulse propagation etc.[6],[9].

Compared to other methods of solving NPDEs, IST method got lot of attentions and least attention given to BT and LST methods. Even now no well accepted definition of BT is developed. In 1875, Backlund who developed BT for a second order NPDE called sine-Gordon equation (SGE) by transforming to a pair of first order coupled NPDEs for developing particular solutions of SGE. Then Clairon extended this method for connecting exact solutions of two different NPDEs, d'Alembert's equation and Liouville's equation [10], called generalized BT (GBT) But such GBT is so far not developed for any other NPDEs. In 1879 S.Lie developed a method to find particular solutions of ordinary differential equations by an one parameter infinitesimal similarity transformation (LST). By LST method a second order differential equations may be able to converted to first order differential equations, when such LST exists. Recently this method of LST further developed to partial differential equations (PDEs) for reduction of number of independent variables. So that a second order PDE with two independent variables may be able to convert second order ordinary differential equations

(ODE) with new independent variable . Both BT and LST are based on contact transformation of surfaces .

In this study it is shown that, the exact particular solutions generated by LST method need not be obtained by the BT or GBT. So that, the general solution form of Liouville's equation generated from general solution of d'Alembert's equation by GBT is restricted to solution in terms functions of $(kx-vt)$ of travelling waves types alone. In addition to that Liouville's equation has other types solutions that can be generated by LST method having both rotational and translational symmetries. Similarly exact solutions developed by BT, IST or Hirota bilinear method need not be generated by LST method for second order PDEs. This differences are shown by finding symmetries of original equations and that of pair of first order PDEs of BT , GBT and LST .

II. Basic Theory of Backlund Transformation

Consider two different surface elements $F(x, y, u, u_x, u_y)$ and $G(x', y', v, v_x', v_y')$. Then there are many ways these two surface elements may be connected . For which there are five distinct equations needed and that related by total differentials,

$$du = u_x dx + u_y dy \quad \text{and} \quad dv = v_x' dx' + v_y' dy'. \quad (2.01)$$

Then there are four independent equations ,

$$F_j(x, y, u, p, q; v, p', q') = 0, \quad \text{for } j= 1, 2, 3, 4. , \quad (2.02)$$

where $p = u_x$, $q = u_y$, $p' = v_x'$, and $q' = v_y'$.

There are cases when the integrals $u(x, y)$ and $v(x, y)$ are integrals of a Monge'-Ampere form is a second order PDE,

$$R w_{xx} + S w_{yy} + T w_{xy} + U (w_{xx} w_{yy} - w_{xy}^2) = V, \quad (2.03)$$

where R, S, T, U and V are functions of x, y, u, u_x and u_y . When variables u and v separately satisfy (2.03) ,then equations can be considered as transformable one another, and such transformation is called Backlund

Transformation (BT). Accordingly, Backlund reported exact particular solutions of sine-Gordon equation (SGE)

$$u_{xy} = \sin(u) , \quad (2.04)$$

by transforming to a pair of first order coupled NPDEs

$$u_{0x} + u_{1x} = \frac{2}{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{u_0 - u_1}{2}\right) , \quad (2.05)$$

and

$$u_{0y} + u_{1y} = 2\beta \sin\left(\frac{u_0 + u_1}{2}\right) , \quad (2.06)$$

where u_0 and u_1 are any two exact solutions of SGE (3.01) and β is the BT parameter. Using above BT exact travelling wave type solution of (2.04) ,

$$u(x,y) = 4 \arctan[\exp(kx - vy)] , \quad (2.07)$$

can be obtained, that represents total negative curvature surface.

In 1902, J.Clarin developed a more simplified method of finding BT for second order PDEs, called generalized BT (GBT) so GBT gives a pair of first order coupled PDEs by which exact solutions of given second order PDEs can be transformed to exact solutions of another PDE. Brief outline of GBT is the following.

Let the given second order PDEs be

$$F(x, y, u, v, u_x, u_y, u_{xx}, u_{xy}, u_{yy}, v_x, v_y, v_{xx}, v_{xy}, v_{yy}) = 0 . \quad (2.04)$$

then the resultant BT is a pair of first order PDEs as,

$$u_x = f(u, v, v_x, v_y) , \quad (2.05)$$

$$u_y = g(u, v, v_x, v_y) . \quad (2.06)$$

Then the integrability condition for (2.05) and (2.06) is,

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y \partial x} - \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} = 0 \quad (2.07)$$

$$= f_u g - g_u f + (f_{v_x} - g_{v_y})v_{xy} + f_{v_y}v_{yy} - g_{v_x}v_{xx} = 0. \quad (2.08)$$

If the integrability condition (2.08) is free of second order derivatives v_{xx} , v_{xy} and v_{yy} then (2.08) becomes

$$(f_{v_x} - g_{v_y}) = 0, f_{v_y} = g_{v_x} = 0, \quad (2.09)$$

such case, according to Clarin the transformation satisfies contact transformation between two surfaces represented by (2.05) and (2.06). Moreover, in that case (2.08) satisfies Monge'-Ampere form (2.03), such case GBT may be able to develop. All cases of (2.03) assures BT, only when four equations with three unknown functions is an essential condition for GBT. Obviously, theory of BT and GBT ignoring the second derivatives appeared in the integrability condition (2.07) and (2.08) so fails to generate general solution of given PDE (2.04), only particular exact solutions may be able to generate.

Clarin's method developed the GBT [9] between Liouville's equation [10],

$$v_{xy} = \exp(v), \quad (2.10)$$

and d'Alemberts equation

$$u_{xy} = 0, \quad (2.11)$$

as a pair of first order PDEs,

$$u_x = v_x + c \exp\left[\frac{(u+v)}{2}\right], \quad (2.12)$$

and

$$u_y = -v_y - \frac{2}{c} \exp\left[\frac{(v-u)}{2}\right], \quad (2.13)$$

where c is a parameter of the GBT.

Clarin's used the 'so called general solution of d'Alembert's equation as,

$$u(x,y) = F(x) + G(y),$$

where $F(x)$ and $G(y)$ are arbitrary functions of x and y respectively then by above GBT (2.12) and (2.13) obtained 'so called general solution ' of Liouville's equation with two arbitrary functions $F(x)$ and $G(y)$ as[10],

$$\text{Exp}(v) = 2 \frac{\frac{\partial F}{\partial x} \frac{DG}{\partial y}}{[F(x) + G(y)]^2} . \quad (2.14)$$

Recently [11] reported improved version of exact solution of d' Alembert's equation (2.11) developed by LST method which have both rotational as well as translational invariant symmetries as

$$u(x, y) = F(x) + G(y) + C_1 \log[S], \quad (2.15)$$

where S is

$$S = [-cxy + (kx - \omega y) + \frac{k\omega}{2c}] . \quad (2.16)$$

Or

$$u(x,y) = F(x) + G(y) + \log[-cxy + (kx - \omega y) + \frac{k\omega}{2c}]^{C_1} . \quad (2.17)$$

where $F(x)$ and $G(y)$ are arbitrary functions of x and y , C_1 , c , k and ω are arbitrary constants of integration and $c \neq 0$.

For (3+1) dimensional case above d'Alembert's equation (2.11) becomes

$$u_{xx} + u_{yy} + u_{zz} - u_{tt} = 0 , \quad (2.18)$$

and the exact solution is

$$u(x, y, z, t) = \log[S_0]^{C_1} \quad (2.19)$$

where S_0 is,

$$S_0 = \{c(x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - t^2) + [(k_1 x - \omega_1 t) + (k_2 x - \omega_2 t) + (k_3 z - \omega_3 t)] - [(\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + \omega_3^2) - (k_1^2 + k_2^2 + k_3^2)]/2c\} , \quad (2.20)$$

where $c, k_i, \omega_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ are arbitrary constants of integration and $c \neq 0$. These two solutions (2.17) and (2.20) are indeterminate forms when $C_1 >$

0, $S=0$ and $S_0=0$. When $C_1 < 0$ both solutions are singular. When $k = \omega = k_i = \omega_i = 0$ for $i=1,2,3$ then both solutions have no translational invariant parts.

Moreover, these new solutions (2.17) different from the 'so called general solution of d' Alembert's equation and so (2.14) is not the general solution of Liouville's equation (2.11).

III. Lie's Similarity Method of Solving Partial differential Equations

Brief outline of the LST method of solving PDE by reducing the number of independent variables by one is the following [04]. Let the given PDE with n number of independent variables and m dependent variables be,

$$\psi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, \omega^1, \omega^2, \dots, \omega^m, \omega_{,k}^i) = 0, \quad (3.01)$$

Where x_j are independent variables and ω^i are dependent variables, $i=1,2,\dots,n$ and $j=1,2,\dots,m$. and $\omega_{,k}^i$ is the partial differential of dependent variable ω^j with respect independent variable x_k . Apply, one infinitesimal parameter $\epsilon > 0$, family of infinitesimal transformations,

$$x_j = x_j + \epsilon X_j(x_i, \omega^i) + O(\epsilon^2), \quad (3.02)$$

$$\omega^i = \omega^i + \epsilon W^i(x_j, \omega^i) + O(\epsilon^2), \quad (3.03)$$

Correspondingly, the first order partial derivatives of dependent variables ω^i are transformed as,

$$\omega_{,k}^i = \omega_{,k}^i + \epsilon [W_{,k}^i] + O(\epsilon^2), \quad (3.04)$$

Where $[W_{,k}^i]$ is called 'first extension' of first order derivatives $\omega_{,k}^i$ of dependent variables ω^i and its expansion as [04],

$$[W_{,k}^i] = \frac{\partial \omega^i}{\partial x_k} + \frac{\partial W^i}{\partial \omega^\mu} \omega_{,k}^\mu - \frac{\partial X_\nu}{\partial x_k} \omega_{,\nu}^i - \frac{\partial X_\nu}{\partial \omega^\mu} \omega_{,k}^\mu \omega_{,\nu}^i. \quad (3.05)$$

The second partial derivatives $\omega_{,jk}^i$ with respect to the variables x_j and x_k are transformed as,

$$\omega^i_{,jk} = \omega^i_{,jk} + \epsilon[W^i_{,jk}] + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{3.06}$$

where $[W^i_{,jk}]$ is called ‘second extension’ of the second order derivatives $\omega^i_{,jk}$ of the dependent variables ω^i with respect to the independent variables x_j and x_k , and its expansion is,

$$\begin{aligned} [W^i_{,jk}] = & \frac{\partial^2 W^i}{\partial x_j \partial x_k} + \frac{\partial^2 W^i}{\partial x_j \partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\mu_{,k} + \frac{\partial^2 W^i}{\partial x_k \partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\mu_{,j} - \frac{\partial^2 X_\nu}{\partial x_j \partial x_k} \omega^i_\nu + \frac{\partial W^i}{\partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\mu_{,jk} \\ & - \frac{\partial X_\nu}{\partial x_j} \omega^i_{,k\nu} - \frac{\partial X_\nu}{\partial x_k} \omega^i_{,j\nu} + \frac{\partial^2 W^i}{\partial \omega^\lambda \partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\lambda_{,j} \omega^\mu_{,k} - \frac{\partial^2 X_\nu}{\partial x_j \partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\mu_{,j} \omega^i_\nu - \frac{\partial^2 X_\nu}{\partial x_k \partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\mu_{,k} \omega^i_\nu \\ & \frac{\partial X_\nu}{\partial \omega^\mu} [\omega^i_\nu \omega^\mu_{,jk} + \omega^\mu_{,j} \omega^i_{,\nu k} + \omega^\mu_{,k} \omega^i_{,j\nu}] - \frac{\partial^2 X_\nu}{\partial \omega^\lambda \partial \omega^\mu} \omega^\lambda_{,k} \omega^\mu_{,j} \omega^i_\nu . \end{aligned} \tag{3.07}$$

The so called “ invariant surface condition”[] for a similarity transformation (3.01), (3.02) and (3.03) of the given PDE (3.01) for a second order PDE is

$$X_i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_i} + W^i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \omega^i} + [W^i_{,j}] \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \omega^i_{,j}} + [W^i_{,jk}] \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \omega^i_{,jk}} = 0. \tag{3.08}$$

On solving above” invariant condition” the similarity transformation under which the given PDE (3.01) can be transform into another PDE with one independent variables less can be found out.

Then for finding the similarity transformation solve,

$$X_j \frac{d\omega^i}{dx_j} + W^i \frac{d\omega^i}{dW^i} = 0 , \tag{3.09}$$

using the Lagrange’s conditions,

The solution of (3.09) gives the similarity variables η_j as function of independent variables x_j and arbitrary constants ,and the ‘similarity solutions’ ω^i as function of similarity variables η_j . On substituting similarity solution in the given PDE (3.01) the resultant equation is called similarity reduced equation having one independent variable less than that of given PDE . All exact solutions of similarity reduced equation is also exact solutions of given PDE (3.01) ,but converse need not be satisfied.

IV. Lie's Similarity Transformation of Generalized Backlund Transformation of Liouville's and D'Alembert's Equations

For (2.12) and (2.13) the “invariant surface conditions” are

$$[U_x] = [V_x] + c([U] + [V]) \exp\left(\frac{u+v}{2}\right), \quad (4.01)$$

and

$$[U_y] = -[V_y] - \frac{2}{c} ([V] - [U]) \exp\left(\frac{v-u}{2}\right). \quad (4.02)$$

Where the first extensions are,

$$[U_x] = U_x + U_u u_x + U_v v_x - (Y_x u_y + X_x u_x) - (Y_u u_x u_y + Y_v v_x u_x) - (X_u u_x v_x + X_v v_x u_x) \quad (4.03)$$

$$[V_x] = V_x + V_u u_x + V_v v_x - (Y_x v_y + X_x v_x) - (Y_u v_y u_x + Y_v v_x v_y) - (X_u u_x v_x + X_v v_x u_x), \quad (4.04)$$

$$[U_y] = U_y + U_u u_y + U_v v_y - (X_x u_x + Y_y u_y) - (Y_u u_y u_x + Y_v v_y u_y) - (X_u u_y u_x + X_v u_x v_y), \quad (4.05)$$

$$[V_y] = V_y + V_u u_y + V_v v_y - (X_x v_x + Y_y v_y) - (Y_u u_x u_y + Y_v v_y u_x) - (X_u u_y v_x + X_v u_y v_x). \quad (4.06)$$

Substitute (4.03) – (4.06) in (4.01) and (4.02) then equate the coefficients of different orders of derivatives of u and v, then essential constraint equations are,

$U = V = 0$, and all derivatives of V, U are zero. . This implies,

$$X = \omega \quad \text{and} \quad Y = k. \quad (4.07)$$

Hence Lagrange's conditions

$$\frac{dx}{X} = \frac{dy}{Y} = \frac{du}{U} = \frac{dv}{V}, \quad (4.08)$$

Yields the similarity solution as

$$\tau(x, t) = (\kappa x - \omega y) . \quad (4.09)$$

Then corresponding above similarity variable $\tau(x, t)$ the similarity solutions of (2.12) and (2.13) are

$$u(x, y) = u(\tau) , \quad (4.10)$$

and

$$v(x, y) = v(\tau) . \quad (4.11)$$

substitute in (2.12) and (2.13) give the respective similarity reduced equations as,

$$\frac{du}{d\tau} = \frac{dv}{d\tau} + c \exp\left(\frac{u+v}{2}\right) , \quad (4.12)$$

and

$$\frac{du}{d\tau} = - \frac{dv}{d\tau} - \frac{2}{c} \exp\left(\frac{v-u}{2}\right) . \quad (4.13)$$

V. Comparison Between Similarity Transformation and Backlund Transformation

Both BT and LST methods are used to find exact particular solutions of PDEs. BT developed by A.V. Backlund is only for connecting solutions of same single PDE so called Auto-Backlund Transformation (ABT). Whereas, Clarin improved ABT for connecting solutions of two different PDEs and so called Generalized BT (GBT) .

Even when fails to find ABT or GBT for a NPDE, that may be LST applicable . Now ABT developed by Backlund applied to SGE ,so far no other PDE solved by that method. GBT method developed by Clarion applied to connect solutions of Liouville's (2.10)and d' alembert's equations(2.11), no other case this method found as successful .Whereas, LST method applicable to many PDEs even system of coupled NPDEs []. Even then there are cases LST method also fails when no similarity variable exists for such PDEs for example the class of Painleve type equations.

In ABT and GBT ,second order of NPDEs transform to first ordered PDEs , so reduction in the number of symmetries of the original PDEs. In SGE (2.04) and in Liouville's equation (2.10) two symmetries are possible including translation ,their common similarity variable is

$$\eta(x, y) = [-cxy + (kx - vy) + \frac{kv}{c}] \quad (5.01)$$

.Whereas, in ABTand GBT the transformed PDEs having only one symmetry ,translation (4.09) alone . This reduction of symmetries reduce the number of physical properties in the system modeled by that PDE. In LST the transformed equation and original PDEs are of same order of derivatives even then there will be symmetry loss . For example SG and d' Alembert's equations or Klein-Gordon (KG) family of equations have translational symmetry but respective similarity reduced equations have translational symmetry exists only along with rotational symmetry, this is due to the peculiar property of existence of second order derivatives in the PDEs, Whereas, in ABT and GBT resultant coupled PDEs having only first order derivatives so no rotational symmetries possible.

According to each symmetries obtained from the LST of a PDE respective different exact similarity reduced PDEs can be found out ,and so that large number of distinct exact solutions can be obtained . In the case of d'Alembert's equation , more improved version of exact solution (4.14) with two symmetries obtained so two distinct types of exact solutions are possible. Such type of variety of distinct solutions for Liouville's equation (2.10) are [12]

$$\exp(u) = 2 \frac{B \eta^{-(n+1)}}{[A+B\eta^{-n}]^2} , \quad (5.02)$$

where A and B are arbitrary constants , $B \neq 0$, n is any rational number both positive and negative , $n \neq 0$ and $n \neq -1$ and $\eta(x, y)$ is the similarity variable (5.01) . Solution (5.02) can not be generated as exact solution of Liouville-s equation through the respective GBT (4.12) and (4.13) due to first order equations having translational symmetry alone .

VI. Conclusion

LST method of finding exact solutions of PDEs yields more symmetries than that of ABT or GBT. It is because in ABT or GBT method, second order PDEs transform to first order PDEs so whatever symmetries associated with second order derivatives losing when ABT or GBT express in terms first order PDEs. By first order PDEs of ABT or GBT there exists only travelling wave type solutions are possible like (2.07) as in SGE. Moreover, such travelling wave solutions obtained by ABT or GBT, can not generate by LST method. Since in LST method travelling wave type solutions as a function of $(kx-vt)$ exists only along with rotationally invariant part as function of (cxy) . All of the known soliton type solutions of travelling wave types have no rotational symmetry part like exact solutions generated by LST method. Moreover, rotational part alone is possible without travelling wave part, such type of exact solutions no other method able to develop other than LST method.

In most cases the nonlinear parts of NPDEs is retain in the similarity reduced equation and so finding exact solution is difficult even in the resultant similarity reduced equations. LST method applicable to many coupled NPDEs whereas, ABT or GBT not developed for coupled PDEs. Although LST, ABT and GBT are all belong to same class of contact transformations of surfaces, generally solutions generated by these methods belong to different sectors of complete solution set of a given NPDEs. Most cases they are mutually exclusive types, as translational invariant alone and other is translational invariant only along with rotational invariant parts. Hence ABT or GBT or LST method not suitable for generating exact general or complete solutions of a NPDEs.

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